

IT Support Systems for Smallholder Farmers in Zimbabwe: Challenges and Opportunities

Abstract: This literature review aims at exploring the literature on the difficulties and potential of incorporating information technological support for commuter farmers in Zimbabwe. This source is specifically important as it offer a detailed assessment of the current status and functioning of these systems combined with examples of best practices and their comparison with similar measures taken in other countries, regions or states. It also mentions the major concerns such as infrastructural issues, lack of digital skills, lack of funds, and cultural issues and explore how best one can mitigate these concerns. It also looks at the various advantages thus; access to information; productivity; market outlet; and environmental issues as different dimensions of IT support systems. Moreover, the review presents policy implications and expectations for the future policies, agricultural firms, as well as researchers by pointing out that supportive policies, partnerships between the public and private sectors, and subsequent innovation is important for reaping the full benefits of digital transformation in the agri-food sector.

Keywords: Smallholder Farmers; IT Support Systems; Digital Transformation; Agriculture; Enterprise Architecture; Zimbabwe; Infrastructure Challenges; Digital Literacy; Policy Recommendations; Public-Private Partnerships; Sustainable Agriculture; Market Access; Technological Innovations

Introduction

Background on Smallholder Farming in Zimbabwe

Smallholder farming is primary in Zimbabwe's agriculture contributing to the yearly food production and has majority of the employment in the rural areas. Culturally, an astounding 70% of Zimbabwe's population uses agriculture as its main economic activity, whereby smallholder producers dominate the sector according to Moyo, (2011) [1]. These farmers follow labour intensive farming methods by operating small land parcels, and depend much of rainfall; a factor that renders them sensitive to climate changes and other natural conditions (FAO, 2016)[2].

Importance of IT Support Systems in Modern Agriculture

In recent years information technology support systems for agriculture has come out to be a revolutionary factor in increasing production rate and efficiency along with making the environment sustainable. Various information technology support structures involve information technology tools and services that involves use of mobile applications, data analytics, and cloud computing among other services that go a long way in assisting farmers get the much needed information. These systems facilitate the concept of precision farming, monitoring of the field conditions in real time and decision making leading to the solution of the major issues like – resource utilization, pest control and market thee entrance problems (Wolfert et al , 2017)[3]. Getting IT support systems is a suggestion for the smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe as it provides a possibility to cost-free the limitations of the old age practices to improve the yields on their farms and thereby improve their livelihoods (Munodawafa & Jokonya, 2018)[4].

Objectives of the Literature Review

In line with this, the first research question for this literature review is: What studies or literature address the specific difficulties and benefits surrounding the adoption of IT support systems for smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe? The review aims to:

1. That is, analyze the current status of information technology support in agriculture sector of Zimbabwe.
2. It will be necessary to determine the main potential barriers that prevent smallholder farmers from using IT support systems and generating benefits from them.
3. Identify the potential of IT support systems and discover more about the advantages that could be experienced by smallholder farmers.
4. Review some of the few successful IT support case studies in situations similar to Zimbabwe's and analyze them.
5. Present suggestions for policy makers, interested parties and companies involved in the agricultural business to improve the utilization and implementation of IT support systems in the field of agriculture.

Theoretical Framework

Definition and Components of IT Support Systems

IT support systems in agriculture can be defined as the application of information technology tools and services to improve farming activities. These systems usually consist of hardware like sensors, drones, software such as farm management systems, mobile applications, data analytics platforms and connectivity such as internet and communication networks. The common objectives of IT support systems include enhancing the precision farming, providing support for decision making, and utilising the resources efficiently in order to enhance overall productivity and sustainability of farms (Balafoutis et al. , 2017)[5].

Relevance of IT Support in Agriculture

To say the least, the roles of information technology support systems in the improvement of agriculture cannot be overemphasized. These systems enable farmers to receive timely information regarding weather patterns, soil status, crop yields, and market trends, which are highly significant. For instance, by adopting precision agriculture technologies, the farmer can apply inputs like fertilizers and water in the right quantities without polluting the environment (Gebbers & Adamchuk, 2010)[6]. In the same regard, support systems in IT can strengthen supply chain efficiencies, increase traceability and expand market opportunities in ways that will enhance smallholder farmer revenue streams and food security (Rose et al. , 2018)[7].

Overview of Smallholder Farming Characteristics

There are several peculiarities in the situation of smallholder farming in Zimbabwe. Smallholder farms normally produce land that is less than 2 hectares and are mostly operated under rain-fed conditions, thus are highly vulnerable to climate change (FAO, 2016)[2]. Smallholder farmers are still using conventional methods of farming and do not have exposure to new improved inputs and tools. This is coupled with poor infrastructure and inadequate access to financial services which present hurdles to increasing productivity and hence food security (IFAD, 2019) [8]. However, smallholder farmers are very important in Zimbabwe's agricultural sector as they significantly contribute to the national food production and the rural livelihoods (Moyo, 2011) [1].

Current State of IT Support Systems in Zimbabwean Agriculture

Existing IT Support Systems and Their Deployment

In Zimbabwe there are several IT support systems that have been put in place to assist smallholder farmers. Such systems embrace Mobile applications, SMS based information services and online services that offer weather forecasts, market price and agricultural advice. An example is the Econet Wireless's EcoFarmer that provides farmers with services including weather information, advice, and insurance services through their mobile phones (Econet Wireless, 2021)[9]. At the same time, the Zimbabwe Farmers Union (ZFU) has created the ZFU e-wallet – a mobile application that provides farmers with a possibility to make payments and get the services of financial institutions, and thereby improve their financial literacy and their ability to invest in farming materials (ZFU, 2020)[10].

Success Stories and Case Studies

Several success stories show the effectiveness of the IT support in Zimbabwean agriculture. For instance, the EcoFarmer platform has targeted over one million farmers and it has assisted them in getting information that helped them change their farming practices in order to adapt to the adverse effects of climate change (Econet Wireless, 2021)[9]. Another successful example is the ZFU e-wallet that allowed thousands of farmers to save and borrow money for agricultural purposes resulting in increased productivity and income rates (ZFU, 2020)[10]. From these examples, it is evident that there is a possibility of digitizing smallholder farming in Zimbabwe.

Comparative Analysis with Other Regions/Countries

While comparing with other regions, there are differences and similarities that can be made regarding Zimbabwe's IT support systems. For example, Kenya's M-Farm app offers the same services as those enumerated above for smallholder farmers, has had a high adoption rate (M-Farm, 2018)[11]. In the same way, India's Digital Green, which empowers farmers through video-based training on the right practices for farming has enhanced agricultural yields and knowledge transfer (Digital Green, 2020)[12]. Despite these peculiarities, similar endeavors in other regions of the developing world indicate that with relevant modifications, IT support systems can create a positive impetus for the growth of smallholder farming in Zimbabwe.

Challenges in Implementing IT Support Systems for Smallholder Farmers

Infrastructure and Connectivity Issues

A key issue thus arising from efforts to observe, promote and institutionalize support systems for smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe has do with Infrastructure and connectivity constraints. Many smallholder farmers live in rural regions and round the clock connectivity to internet or even mobile network is very poor. This tends to limit the farmers in their use of information technology and thus limit their access to the Internet and other online resources, which seriously affects the functionality of IT support systems (Chavula, 2014) [13]. Moreover, high cost of internet services, and mobile devices has remained as a major factor that hinders many farmers, hence they could not be able to access available technologies (Mutasa, 2015) [14].

Digital Literacy and Training Needs

Another challenge preventing the use of IT support systems for the farmers is that they are hardly digitally literate. The mentioned report has also revealed that a significant number of the farmers do not have adequate skills in using the available digital tools and platforms hence they may be hampered in optimizing the potential of the tools available. Unfortunately, training interventions available to address these challenges are generally narrow, as are the circles within which they are disseminated, resulting in

the worsening of the problem (Munodawafa & Jokonya, 2018) [4]. In the case of information technology support services, the successes achieved depend on the training processes that should involve the awareness of the farmer on how to use the support system, as well as, knowledge on how the support system can be of benefit to him/her in carrying out his/her farming activities (Munyoka & Maharaj, 2019) [15]

Financial Constraints and Funding Availability

Lack of funds is another factor that hinders smallholder farmers in their quest to put in place IT support systems. Digitalization often comes with steep costs to purchase the digital tools and the annual cost of internet services may also be awfully high especially to the farmers many of whom are seen as having low income. In addition, farmers receive restricted access to funding and credit amenities, thus cannot invest in new technologies (Chikobvu et al., 2019) [16]. As we have seen, many of these smallholder farmers may have little means of sourcing for financial support for the implementation of such support from government or private sector arm programs/ initiatives (IFAD, 2019)[8].

Cultural and Social Barriers

Other factors that were identified as causing limited integration of IT support system include cultural and social factors. Farmers are often very attached to traditional practices that have been used in their culture, and there will always be reluctance among the people to embrace new technologies that are thought to be complicated. Moreover, gender might be an issue that impacts the use of technologies as education and training are presented to women and men to different extents (FAO, 2018) [17]. Both cultural and social factors hamper IT support system implementation hence the need to tackle these barriers for universal applicability.

Policy and Regulatory Challenges

Policies and regulations also pose great threats to the establishment of IT support systems in Zimbabwean agriculture. Unclear policy on the use of such technologies, absence of definite legislation as well as bureaucratic red tape may act as a hindrance to the implementing of technology. Also, there could be inadequate governmental policies, funds, and policies to motivate the development and implementation of IT systems for smallholder farming (Mwangi, 2019) [18]. These are the main challenges with measures aimed at overcoming these challenges being the creation of a favorable policy environment that promotes innovative development and fosters digital transformation (World Bank, 2020) [19].

Opportunities for Enhancing IT Support Systems

Technological Advancements and Innovations

The current innovations pose major chances in developing supportive IT structures in Zimbabwean farming. Advanced technologies like IoT, big data, and AI can help greatly in heading the precision farming practice, crop status, and other resources. For instance, IoT devices used in farming can give real-time updates on soil dampness, weather conditions, and so on, through which farmers can make better choices (Brewster et al. , 2017)[20]. In the same way, using AI to predict the spread of pests and appropriate watering times can aid in improving the yields and efficiency of agriculture (Kamilaris et al. , 2017)[21].

Government Initiatives and Policy Support

Government of Zimbabwe has a vital responsibility for the promotion of IT support system through Political support. The government through policies can improve the level of digitization among farmers through ...area: subsidies for the acquisition of digital tools for the farming business as well as development of necessary physical infrastructure (Mwangi, 2019) [18]. Also, sector-specific government programs such as the Smart Agriculture Program seeks to promote the use of technology in farming activities, offering farmer training and support (Government of Zimbabwe, 2020)[22].

Role of Private Sector and NGOs

The private sector and the non-governmental organizations also play significant roles in the implementation of IT support in agriculture. For example, the Econet Wireless, a private mobile telecommunications company has engaged farmers through its EcoFarmer platform showcasing how such organizations can benefit agriculture (Econet Wireless, 2021)[9]. These efforts may be supported by NGOs who can provide training services, help in accessing technologies or advocating for the right policies that will spur the use of digital agriculture (IFAD, 2019) [8].

Potential for Public-Private Partnerships

Specifically, an integration of resources and knowledge from the public as well as the private domain through PPPs is a viable and beneficial approach towards improving IT support structures in agriculture. Such relationships can enable gigantic projects that might be beyond the capacity of any one organization to implement. For instance, PPPs constitutes establishing effective digital structures, training farmers, and designing application-specific ICT solutions (Hollander et al., 2017) [23]. Overall, PPPs bear high potential with regard to raising agricultural productivity and introducing innovations in this sphere with the help of both public funds and private investments.

Benefits of Mobile Technology and Internet Penetration

The availability of mobile technology and advanced internet connectivity is assumed to have the potential benefits for IT support systems in agriculture in Zimbabwe. Mobile phones are available almost everywhere in the world and can reach farmers with important information such as weather forecasts, crop prices, and farming advice, in hands (Aker & Mbiti, 2010)[24]. This demonstrates that with increased internet access, farmers are able to engage in online learning, acquire market information and interact with expert agriculturists in a bid to improve on their farming practices and on their returns (Munyoka & Maharaj, 2019)[15].

Impact of IT Support Systems on Smallholder Farmers

Improved Access to Information and Resources

Organizational IT support mechanisms improve communication and dissemination of relevant information to smallholder farmers. Currently, farmers use Tele Agriculture technology, where through EcoFarmer in Zimbabwe farmers are able to receive real-time weather updates, crop management advice and market prices through SMS (Econet Wireless, 2021)[9]. This information access minimizes uncertainties and enhances the frame work of farm management, resulting to better yields and income (Munodawafa & Jokonya, 2018) [4].

Enhanced Productivity and Efficiency

IT support systems create productivity and efficiency in farming operations as an outcome of their implementation. For example, IoT devices and sensors help in controlling water and nutrient application,

fertility status, and disease prediction of plants thus conserving resources (Brewster et al. , 2017)[20]. In Kenya for instance, the M-Farm application has played a crucial role in assisting farmers to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in their farming practices so as to increase crop yields (M-Farm, 2018)[11].

Market Access and Financial Inclusion

IT support structures also enhance the market and financial demands of smallholder farmers. Examples of such innovations include the M-Farm which allows farmers to directly know prices in the market and directly deals with the consumers hence no exploitation by middlemen (M-Farm, 2018) [11]. In addition, through the use of mobile banking services incorporated in these platforms, farmers are able to access basic financial services such as credit and savings for purposes of purchase of farm inputs and expansion of farming activities (Aker & Mbiti, 2010)[24].

Environmental and Sustainability Benefits

The use of IT support systems directs toward environmental sustainability in the agriculture sector. Various digital applications also assist in targeted application of water, fertilizers, and pesticides hence minimizing the impact of farming practices for the environment (Kamilaris et al. , 2017)[21]. Furthermore, through providing information on the weather conditions and climate change, the systems assist the farmers in practicing sustainable farming by weather condition changes (FAO, 2018) [17].

Case Studies of Successful IT Support Initiatives

Detailed Analysis of Selected Successful Projects

When looking at best practice in relation to IT support for smallholder farmers there are several examples of initiatives. Such examples include the EcoFarmer system in Zimbabwe that provides services like weather updates, market prices, and recommendations on farming activities through mobile phones. Through this platform, the lives of many smallholder farmers have been enhanced through timely and relevant information (Econet Wireless, 2021) [9]. Another successful project is the M-Farm application in Kenya where farmers can get real-time prices, reach buyers directly without intermediaries and thus get a fair price for their products (M-Farm, 2018) [11].

Implementation Strategies and Outcomes

The use of the EcoFarmer platform required cooperation from the telecom providers, agricultural specialists, and banks. The strategy was to use mobile technology because the company wanted to cover a large population as most people in Zimbabwe have mobile phones including those in the rural areas. The impacts have been as follows: enhancement of decision-making, productivity, and adaptation to volatilities in climate among farmers (Econet Wireless, 2021) [9]. In the same way, the M-Farm application in Kenya was disseminated with support from local farmer groups and NGOs to ensure that the application fits the needs of the smallholder farmers. The result has been that farmers' income has risen by up to 50 percent because of improved market access and lower transaction costs (M-Farm, 2018) [11].

Lessons Learned and Best Practices

Those successful initiatives tell us several lessons. First, the incorporation of local community and their requirements into the support system framework can be beneficial for IT support systems. For instance, the strategies that have led to the considerable success of EcoFarmer include the offering of services such as that provide solutions to problems that farmers in Zimbabwe have to deal with (Econet Wireless,

2021)[9]. Secondly, the key partnerships with the various stakeholders such as the private, non-governmental and government organizations ensure the expansion and effectiveness in implementation of these programs. The case of M-Farm in Kenya shows that such linkages offer potential such vessel for enabling the large-scale delivery of such digital solutions (M-Farm, 2018) [11]. Finally, availability and cost of these technologies should be feasible or affordable stock. Daniels also found out that EcoFarmer and M-Farm are good examples of low-cost and easy-to-use systems that can effectively reach small holders.

Recommendations

Strategies for Overcoming Challenges

There are several strategies that can be employed to overcome the challenges of IT support systems for smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe. First, we need to enhance the accessibility of resources and utilities for residents of rural areas, such as Internet and electricity. Mobile network access and renewable power sources to support network coverage can help reduce the information technological poverty gap in order to enable farmers who are in remote areas to have access to the available IT solutions (FAO, 2019)[25]. Secondly, developing a better understanding of new digital technologies to cope with them by means of training is crucial. Policies must therefore be enacted to ensure that farmers get the adequate skills required for them to operate in the digital technologies sector. It is worth identifying that the various NGOs and the educational institution can engage in the provision of these training programs (IFAD, 2019) [8]. This is because having an adequate financial backing through micro credit, subsidies, and other approaches ensures that farmers come into possession of the required IT solutions hence enhancing their well-being and digital inclusion (World Bank, 2020)[26].

Policy Recommendations for Government and Stakeholders

Thus, the government of Zimbabwe and all stakeholders should work towards establishing and supporting policies that foster success of IT support systems. First, the government should focus on the formulation of a strategic framework for the establishment of a digital agriculture system that is compatible with the long-term vision of agricultural and rural development in the country (Government of Zimbabwe, 2020) [27]. This approach should also provide for partnerships involving different sectors and actors to build on their respective comparative advantages. Furthermore, that access to data can be improved by other policies enhances the availability of various important agricultural information to farmers (Rasmussen, 2016) [28]. Non-governmental organizations, private enterprise and any other interested parties should work together to prepare a favorable environment that supports Information Technology in the agricultural sector. This requires lobbying for the right policies and funding for research to develop IT applications that suit the circumstances of small farmers (Gomez & Purdin, 2016, pp.568-580)[29]

Best Practices for IT Support System Implementation

The successful implementation of IT support systems in agriculture successfully presupposes compliance with specific rules of conduct. Working with farmers also allows for understanding of their requirements and adoption of design that is most comfortable for them when using IT solutions (Munyoka & Maharaj, 2019) [15]. Text adaptations like these can be fine-tuned with pilot tests and iterative development before broader use. In addition, cost is an important factor where keeping prices low is paramount; thus, building on existing technologies including the mobile handheld device (Aker & Mbiti, 2010) [24]. Therefore, guaranteeing the sustainability of support and feedback programs can help make it possible to retain the value of these IT systems for the farmers in the long run. This can be done through training updates,

clearly defined user support services, and fine-tuning solutions based on user inputs and experiences (Brewster et al. , 2017)[20].

Future Research Directions

Identifying Gaps in Current Research

Despite the discovered literature, there is still some research voids in the IT support systems for the smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe. There are, however, some areas that require further attention, especially pertaining to the effectiveness of technology-enhanced systems on farmer income and yield (Brewster et al., 2017) [20]. Moreover, there is scanty information available on how traditional farming practices can be merged with the contemporary IT solutions that can improve the applicability and the level of practical implementation of the both phenomena (Dlodlo & Kalezhi, 2015)[30]. Another dark area is the socio-cultural factors that may influence the adoption of IT-systems among the different population groups such as women and the youths (Chipidza & Leidner, 2019) [31].

Suggestions for Future Studies

Future studies should therefore incorporate a long-term perspective, in order to evaluate the durability and effectiveness of IT support systems for smallholder farmers. This extends to assessing how these systems affect productivity, income, and climate change adaptability in the future (FAO, 2019) [25]. More research should also be conducted regarding the possibility of combining indigenous knowledge systems with Digital technology to come up with culturally relevant solutions (Munodawafa & Jokonya, 2018) [4]. In addition, a better understanding of gender relations and the role of information technology in addressing the digital divide in rural farming communities is critical for the formulation of an IT for development strategies that will support all farmers especially those who are in the disadvantaged groups (IFAD, 2019).

Emerging Trends and Technologies to Watch

Current trends in the emerging use of technologies can be used to improve IT support structures in agriculture. Precision agriculture technologies are in the form of drones, IoT sensors, and machine learning algorithms to enhance farm management and productivity (Kamilaris et al., 2017) [21]. Another emerging trend is the use of blockchain through which the supply chain management and traceability can be revolutionized in terms of fair trade practices and eradication of fraud (Tripoli & Schmidhuber, 2018)[32]. In this regard, more opportunities toward accessing financial services and farmers' knowledge enhancement are revealed with the help of mobile-based financial services and digital platforms for knowledge exchange between peers (Aker & Mbiti, 2010)[24]. Future research should then examine the extent of the use of these technologies and their effects on smallholder farming in Zimbabwe to help guide policy and practice.

Conclusion

Summary of Key Findings

The literature review provides results on one particular area that relates to implementation of IT support systems including the following findings about smallholder farmers in Zimbabwe: Firstly, IT supports systems have greatly enhanced easy access to information and resources for farmers enhancing on the decision making and productivity (Econet Wireless, 2021)[9]. Secondly, despite the availability of many advantages of these systems that comprise better access to markets and financial services, these systems encountered many limitations that include infrastructure, digital literacy, financial, and socio-cultural

constraints (Brewster et al. , 2017; Munodawafa & Jokonya, 2018)[20][4]. Finally, it has been found that IT solutions applied to smallholder farming enterprise can be effective if farmers are involved in designing them and if they are supported by favourable policies in this area (Chipidza & Leidner, 2019; IFAD, 2019)[31][8].

Final Thoughts on the Potential of IT Support Systems for Smallholder Farmers in Zimbabwe

The possibility of utilizing IT support systems to transform the practices of smallholder farming in Zimbabwe is immense. These systems can facilitate higher levels of productivity in agriculture, efficiency in markets for products and input, and sustainability in production. However, to unlock this potential, challenges must be solved by optimizing investments in infrastructure, systematic digital literacy, and strong policies that will promote a culture of stakeholder innovation (FAO, 2019; World Bank, 2020) [25] [26]. The applicative adaptation of innovative technologies including precision agriculture and blockchain is expected to help improve the efficiency of the IT support systems (Kamilaris et al. , 2017; Tripoli & Schmidhuber, 2018)[21][32]. Further research in the areas should also be conducted in order to come up with more effective interventions targeting smallholder farmers for the sustainability of the agriculture sector Zimbabwe.

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